

and figure). Yuanfengzao and Zhe 85-2 that headed at >35 °C had higher SFP (76.8, and 76.2, respectively) than Erjiunan 1 and Erjiufeng (34.9 and 58.1,

respectively).

There was a significantly negative correlation between SFP and mean daily maximum temperature (MMT) 3 d

after heading. SFP decreased with increasing MMT. The critical day for significantly decreased SFP was 30 Jun, when MMT was 35.9 °C for 3 d. □

Grain quality and nutritional value

Using silica gel desiccant to dry rough rice samples

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The method and rate by which rough rice is dried changes the characteristics by which grain quality is judged. We have developed a method that achieves high standardization of large numbers of small samples of grain (less than 1 kg). It is based on the sorptive capacity of a special grade of silica gel mixed directly with field-wet rice.

Intermediate density (ID) grade silica gel is dried, cooled, mixed with field-wet rice in the ratio 1:2 by weight, and the mixture sealed in a moistureproof container. After 24 h, the 2 constituents are separated by screening.

The figure shows the linear regression of field (input) moisture content on residual (output) moisture content within 20–30% wet basis for the model

$$Y = 4.17 \times 0.38; r = 0.91, p = 0.01.$$

Effect of contact mix with ID silica gel on rice input and output moisture content.

Grain quality was measured as grain breakage on milling. The table compares gel-dried samples with sun- and air-dried samples. The gel technique produced

results at least as good as, and some better than, traditional methods, with higher control and resource optimization. □

Moisture content and milling quality of rice dried in a contact mix with ID silica gel and by air and sun.

Drying process	Moisture content (%)		Milling quality (% brown rice)	
	Initial	Residual	Degree of milling	Broken grain
				BR1
Gel	19.2	12.4	16.1 a	20.2 a
Air	19.2	14.3	15.8 a	21.2 ab
Sun	19.2	14.1	15.9 a	21.7 b
				BR3
Gel	24.6	13.7	13.5 a	10.4 a
Air	24.6	14.1	13.0 a	10.4 a
Sun	24.6	14.5	12.5 a	9.1 a
				BR4
Gel	27.1	14.5	13.2 a	5.0 a
Air	27.1	15.6	13.9 b	5.3 a
Sun	27.1	13.2	13.0 a	5.6 a
				BR10
Gel	28.9	15.2	14.0 a	6.2 ab
Air	28.9	14.8	15.1 b	6.6 b
Sun	28.9	13.9	14.4 a	5.9 a

In a column for a variety, means followed by the same letter are not significantly different by DMRT at $p = 0.05$.

Disease resistance

Resistance to sheath blight (ShB) in China

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ShB caused by *Rhizoctonia solani* [Thanatephorus cucumeris (Frank) Donk] is a major disease in the rice areas along the middle and lower reaches of the Yangtze River and in South China. In 1985–87, we used Tetep, IET4699, Jawa no. 14, and Yedao as resistance donors and IR9752-71-3-2 as

susceptible parent to study the inheritance of reaction to artificial ShB inoculation at booting by virulent isolate RH-9, collected in Jiangsu Province.

The F₁ of four combinations of moderately resistant and susceptible parents showed intermediate reaction to inoculation; the F₂ distributions tended to be continuous. That implies that resistance to ShB is controlled by multiple genes (see figure). Broad and narrow sense heritabilities estimated from the cross IR9752-71-3-2/IET4699 were $h^2B = 0.516 + 0.0654$ (broad) and $h^2N = 0.373 + 0.063$ (narrow).

Analysis of combining abilities based on the performance of 28 diallelic F₁s